

Distilling the neural code for word recognition

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Abstract:

Learning to read fluently is associated with the precise encoding of letter position that enables us to distinguish anagrams such as TRIAL and TRAIL. However, the neural basis of how letters and their positions are encoded in our brain is yet unknown. In this study, we trained deep neural network-based models on different languages and found that some units in the later layers of the network are tuned to letter identity. Next, by dissociating the absolute word position, with the relative position of a preferred letter within a word, we tracked how these networks transit from retinotopic to ordinal letter-position coding scheme. Our simulations posit that the units in early layers encode blank spaces at the edges of a word, which are pooled together to encode the ordinal positions of the edge letters irrespective of word position. These predictions are further validated using fMRI studies. Overall, we propose a new schema on how letter positions might be encoded in our brain.

Keywords: word recognition; deep neural networks; reading; position coding

Introduction

Learning to read fluently is an important milestone in education that requires years of practice. It causes widespread changes in our brain and eventually leads to the formation of a specialized region known as Visual Word Form Area (VWFA) (Dehaene et al., 2010, 2015; Dehaene-Lambertz et al., 2018). It also increases the compositionality of visual word representation, thereby increasing the dissimilarity between letter shapes and words of the known script (Agrawal et al., 2019, 2022). Several cognitive models are proposed to predict word recognition behavior. However, they rely on explicit information about letter's position (Norris, 2013). At the retinal level, the position of letters within a word could vary based on size, font, spacing etc., which across multiple stages of processing are transformed into relative rather than absolute spatial reference frame. In this study, we aim to investigate the neural basis of this transformation by simulating literacy acquisition in deep convolutional neural networks. We observed a gradual increase in ordinal position coding in later layers of the network. Next, using 7T fMRI we localized the neural

basis of retinotopic coding in early visual areas and that of ordinal letter position coding in the Visual Word Form Area (VWFA).

Methods

Model architecture and training:

In this study, we chose CORnet-Z architecture for two reasons: 1) It has a modular structure that resembles the stages of processing in the visual cortex (V1, V2, V4, IT, avgpool IT or H, output), 2) It has fewer parameters, thus lowering the training time while achieving high levels of accuracy on synthetic word datasets (Hannagan et al., 2021). Similar to our previous work, we first trained this network on ImageNet dataset (phase 1), which contains ~1.3 million images across 1000 categories. This was considered an illiterate network, which encodes the visual properties of objects but not text. Next, we extended the number of output nodes to 2000 (1000 images + 1000 words), with full connectivity to the H layer units, and retrained the entire network jointly on ImageNet and synthetic word dataset (phase 2), which also contained 1.3 million images across 1000 words. This was considered a literate network.

Stimuli:

The ImageNet images were transformed using standard operations such as "RandomResizedCrop" and "Normalize". In the word dataset, the default scale parameter of RandomResizedCrop was changed such that 90% of the original image was retained. For fair comparisons, other operations such as flipping were not performed on the Imagenet dataset as the same operation would create mirror words in the Word dataset, which is not typical in reading. The synthetic word dataset comprised of 1000 French words (3 – 8 letters long) that varied in size, position, font, etc. There were 1300 exemplars within each word category to match the size of the Imagenet Dataset.

Word selective unit:

Similar to fMRI localiser analysis, a unit was identified as word selective if its mean responses to words were

greater than the mean responses of faces, houses, bodies, and tools + 3 standard deviations across nonword stimuli responses.

Results

To distinguish between anagrams, such as TRIAL and TRAIL, the network must learn to encode the ordinal letter position along with the letter identity. To investigate this mechanism, we first identified word selective units within each layer i.e., units that responds more to words compared to other image categories (see methods). As expected, the proportion of these units increased gradually along the deeper layers of the network i.e., from ~1.5 % in the initial layer (V1) to ~20% in the later layer (H) of the network.

For each of these word selective units, we identified their most preferred and the least preferred stimuli based on their response to individual letters. These letters were then used to create a stimulus set that dissociated between the retinotopic based coding (absolute position on the image) and ordinal position coding (relative position) (Figure 1A). We hypothesized that the units that encode absolute letter position would have a diagonal response profile (Figure 1B left) and those encoding relative letter position would have vertical response profile (Figure 1B right).

Figure 1: (A) Schematic of the stimuli used to dissociate absolute vs relative coding. The word position varies across rows, and the preferred letter position within a string varies across columns. In this example, the preferred letter is 'o', and the unpreferred letter is 'x'. '-' represents blank space. (B) Expected response profile of units with absolute letter position coding (left) and relative letter position coding (right). Each colour represents a different unit.

Figure 2: Exemplar units from each layer of the French literate network. The unit-id and the string comprising preferred and unpreferred letter is displayed on the top. Darker shades represent higher response.

In our networks, we indeed observe such units and a change in their proportion across layers. While units in early layers encoded absolute letter position, the later layers of the network had mixed selectivity and encoded both absolute and relative letter position. The response profiles for a few example units are shown (Figure 2). Further analysis revealed that units in the initial layers of the network (upto V4) encoded blank space, which were pooled together to encode relative letter position coding in IT and H layers.

To validate the proposed mechanism of invariant position coding, we recorded the neural responses using 7T fMRI on the same stimulus set. While early visual areas encoded absolute position of string, we observed ordinal letter position coding in Visual Word Form Area (VWFA).

Discussion

In this study, we investigated the mechanism and neural basis of ordinal letter position code that helps us distinguish between anagrams like TRIAL and TRAIL. We propose a simple mechanism where units in early layers encode blank space and their responses are pooled together to form units that preferentially encode edge letters. Our simulations confirm the findings of several psychological studies that observed larger sensitivity to changes in edge letters than middle letters (Grainger & Whitney, 2004). Further, as hypothesized in LCD model (Dehaene et al., 2005), we localized the neural basis of ordinal position coding in Visual Word Form Area (VWFA).

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